

3Pi Project

KU Leuven Basic Sequence & Nomenclature Document NBMSI

Version 1.0

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Basic sequence	Nomenclature
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INTRO

This document was created to provide an insight on the basic acquisition sequence applied with the Narrow Band Multi-Spectral Imaging (NBMSI) system used at the KU Leuven (for the document on that systems' hardware, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3607302>). It also provides information on the automated file naming (nomenclature) of the captures with that NBMSI system when the Spectral XV software interface for capture and (pre-)processing is used. At KU Leuven this NBMSI infrastructure has been obtained and is being operated within the framework of this 3Pi Project (*Diagnosis of Papyrus-Paper-Parchment manuscripts through advanced Imaging*, AKUL/17/001, FWO: I009918N).⁷

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This NBMSI system was created by R.B. Toth and Associates LLC, in association with Equipose Imaging LLC and Phase One A/S and their local partners; the acquisition software of the system is Spectral XV.

BASIC SEQUENCE, OR, KU LEUVEN BASIC MS SEQUENCE (KULBMSS)

The narrow band multi-spectral imaging system at the KU Leuven (since 2019) uses light panels⁸ with 16 sets of narrow band LEDs and a filter wheel⁹ including 1 bandpass and 4 longpass filters and one unpopulated slot. With these multiple narrow band light sources and filters a sequence of images can be captured automatically driven by the Spectral XV software. For each sequence the result is a **stack** which includes the number of pre-defined recordings. Basically 3 types of images are created:

- **Reflection:** the aim is to capture with the light sensor of the camera the reflections of one of the narrow band light sources which is casted on the imaged object. Practical, each of the sets of narrow band LED's are illuminated after each other; each time an image is taken with pre-defined settings (exposure time, aperture & ISO); in most cases no filter is positioned in between the object and the lens/sensor; and the reflection can be registered by the light sensor.¹⁰
- **Fluorescence/Luminescence:** the aim is to capture the fluorescence (UV → in VIS) or luminescence (any emitted light → longer wavelengths compared to emitted light) effect by the materials in the object when the narrow band light sources are casting energy (light) on the imaged object. A selection of sets of narrow band LEDs (those with a shorter wavelength) illuminate the object; the energy in that light makes the materials (atomic level) – some very strongly, others only limited – at the surface of that object emit light in a longer wavelength; a specific long pass filter between the object and the lens/sensor blocks the reflected wavelengths of the original narrow band light source (i.e. with the same wavelength) and passes only the longer wavelengths which come from the fluorescence/ luminescence effect; the energy of those wavelengths is registered by the light sensor.
- **Dark:** The reflection and the potential fluorescence/ luminescence (=light energy) is registered when no set of narrow band emitters in the light panel is illuminated. In theory, when all recordings take place in a dark room (darkened room) the registered light by the

⁸ See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3607302>.

⁹ Idem.

¹⁰ Note, the exposure times for reflection captures are kept low (UV illuminations are the exceptions); that also limits the fluorescence/luminescence (requires longer exposure times to register the effect in full) which also takes place during these captures; and thus, does not eliminate it. Only reflection captures combined with filter blocking the fluorescence/luminescence effect (blocking wavelengths longer compared to those emitted) can be defined as true reflection results; e.g. in the KULBMSS below only capture 17 can be defined as a true reflection capture.

light sensor should be 0; practical, the dark-capture allows to register how dark the dark room really is.

For the basic sequence – which was labelled KU Leuven Basic MS Sequence (KULBMSS) – the capture settings are outlined according to a fixed scheme: first the reflection captures, secondly the fluorescence/luminescence captures and thirdly the dark-capture. The table below list the KULBMSS in the order as the Spectral XV system makes the captures. The overview below of the KULBMSS contains information regarding the wavelength of the sets of narrow band emitters used for that capture, if and which filter is used, and the camera settings: exposure time, aperture (f) and ISO. This information is also included in the nomenclature (see below) and/or in the EXIF and IPTC metadata fields embedded in each capture (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3607364>).

The KULBMSS (2019 - ...)

Standard, a stacks is captured with the Phase One XF IQ4 150MP Achromatic Camera System, a AF Macro 120mmLS F4 lens (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3607302>), at 900dpi (on the Kaiser copystand that implies a distance of 109,5cm between the position of the object – position of light sensor in camera).¹¹ The recording time of the KULLBMSS takes 10m45s; the field is approximately 40x30cm. The stack of the KULBMSS counts 27 captures:

Table 1 – the KU Leuven Basic MS Sequence (KULBMSS)

	Type	Wavelength	Filter	Exposure	f	ISO
001	reflection	365	None	15s	16	200
002	reflection	385	None	13s	16	200
003	reflection	410	None	1/2s	16	200
004	reflection	420	None	1/2s	16	200
005	reflection	450	None	0.4s	16	200
006	reflection	480	None	1/3s	16	200
007	reflection	510	None	0.6s	16	200
008	reflection	530	None	0.8s	16	200
009	reflection	550	None	1/3s	16	200
010	reflection	600	None	1.6s	16	200
011	reflection	630	None	0.8s	16	200
012	reflection	640	None	1/2s	16	200
013	reflection	660	None	1/2s	16	200
014	reflection	740	None	1.3s	16	200
015	reflection	850	None	4s	16	200

¹¹ But this can be deviated from, see the IPTC description field in the embedded metadata of images captured with this system.

016	reflection	940	None	8s	16	200
017	reflection	365	BP365 (U)	40s	16	800
018	fluorescence	365	LP515 (G)	15s	16	800
019	fluorescence	410	LP515 (G)	15s	16	800
020	fluorescence	420	LP515 (G)	15s	16	800
021	fluorescence	450	LP515 (G)	15s	16	800
022	fluorescence	365	LP590 (R)	15s	16	800
023	fluorescence	410	LP590 (R)	15s	16	800
024	fluorescence	420	LP590 (R)	15s	16	800
025	fluorescence	450	LP590 (R)	15s	16	800
026	fluorescence	385	LP400 (V)	30s	16	800
027	reflection	000	None	1s	16	200

NOMENCLATURE

For every capture in the stack the Spectral XV system automatically generates a file name for that image. That automated file naming is based on information derived from **A.** the created project in the Spectral XV system of which the stack capture is part of, and **B.** some of the selected settings in the captured stack itself; unique for one particular capture only.

➤ Nomenclature of generated file name:

**[ProjectName]_[SceneName]-[StackName]-
[NarrowBandWavelength][Filter]_[StackIndexNumber]_[ProcessingStatus]**

- **[ProjectName]:** free field, as specified in Spectral XV (no spaces)
- **[SceneName]:** free field, as specified in Spectral XV (no spaces)
- **[StackName]:** free field, as specified in Spectral XV (no spaces)
- **[NarrowBandWavelength]:** specific value, one of these seventeen¹²
- **[Filter]:** specific value, one of these six¹³; they are the abbreviations for no filter,¹⁴ or a specific applied filter¹⁵

¹² Narrow band peak wavelength in nanometer: 365, 385, 410, 420, 450, 480, 510, 530, 550, 600, 630, 640, 660, 740, 850, 940, 000. The value '000' represent a dark capture, i.e. none of the narrow band LEDs in the light panel is illuminated.

¹³ N, U, V, G, R, I.

¹⁴ N = when no filter is applied

¹⁵ U = when the BP365 (i.e. ultraviolet band pass filter) is applied

V = when the LP400 (i.e. violet long pass filter) is applied

G = when the LP515 (i.e. green long pass filter) is applied

R = when the LP590 (i.e. red long pass filter) is applied

I = when the LP715 (i.e. infrared long pass filter) is applied

- **[StackIndexNumber]**: specific value, the number (3 digits) of the order in which the image was captured throughout the KULBMSS
- **[ProcessingStatus]**: specific value, one of these two¹⁶, reveals whether image is 'flattened' (LCC) or without 'flattening'¹⁷

➤ Example of a generated file name based on nomenclature

Project54_Scene04-StackRecto-420G_020

➤ The file extension of the captured RAW image is standard IIQ. Additionally a jpg-file is created on the fly as quick reference. After initial processing in the Spectral XV software, tiff-files are generated based on the IIQ file. It are these tiff-files which are regarded as the preservation copies.

SPECTRAL XV SOFTWARE

The Spectral XV software, version 2.1.0.0 (R. B. Toth Associates LLC/Equipoise Imaging LLC) is an integrated capture package controlling the camera, lens, filter wheel combo and Eureka Light panels. Using Phase One's COPE (Capture One Processing Engine) library, the Spectral XV software allows streamlined image capture and metadata operations. It also performs preprocessing operations that result in final output images for visual or further quantitative analysis and visualization using Paleo Toolbox processing software provided by Equipoise Imaging, LLC.

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¹⁶ R, F

¹⁷ R = when image is not flattened (i.e. raw result)
 F = when image is flattened (i.e. flattened result)

